

Features in Assessing the Psychosocial Approaches Based on the Feedback – Received and Transmitted Emotions

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Abstract: *The fairness and efficiency of the learning - teaching process result from the behaviour changes of the designed activity. If the evaluation of the behaviour in a psychometric way in physical education implies probes and tests where the running timing, number of repetitions the long jump, the evaluation of the psychosocial approaches can be done through the means of some tests which combine the students motricity with the survey on students, with the aim of finding out the social involvement level of each student. The experimental research emphasises the way the tests are banded, under the influence of motor activities for the 2nd form students, in three different schools in Arges. The former test, following Zlate Mielu model, aims at the assessment of the training/ development/ education level of the personality features through the learning of every individual psychosocial profile. The latter test is illustrative of Zapan Gheorghe method and implies the examining of objective appreciation capacity concerning the right way of performing all the exercises and the student capacity of obeying the rules. Through the means of these two tests the students social behaviour is assessed on the ground of each students the feedback provided by the emotion received or sent to the students. As a result of this research, we concluded that the psychosocial approaches were included in a prosocial behaviour, each and every student being able to show safety and self - confidence in their own psychometric prospective, as well as fairness regarding their colleagues potential quality.*

Keywords: *objective appreciation/ self-appreciation; psychosocial profile; evaluation; physical education.*

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1. Introduction

Nowadays schools are under pressure due to the concern of the parents regarding the way children perform in schools! We can notice that the focus is more and more concentrated on the profile of the academic achievement and not on the profile of the children's social forming. School pays more attention to the growth of scoring than to the fruition of the educational values (Salamuddin & Harun, 2010).

We share the opinion to which the value of physical education has grown when the physical activities besides the contribution of the physical movement concerning the development and social attitudes through the motive power skills and the affirmation of personality (Epuran, 1976, pp.10-11). Physical education and sport develop and teach a complex domain of interests, needs, motivations, modesty, honesty, distributive attention, determination, perseverance, decision, ambition, initiative, all these intellectual abilities and moral qualities being endowed with high durability and efficiency within the physical activities (Ganciu & Ganciu, 2013, p.116). Moreover, the contribution of the physical education has a great impact on the society: firstly lower costs of health, secondly a lower level of stress, thirdly a higher productiveness among the members of the society, all these together offer the solution to a fluent social integration (Vasiliu, 2015, pp.1442-1443).

The social integration through the motive power activities appears as an interactive process of discovery, assimilation and practising the sportive values as well as the fair-play, team spirit, devotion, competence, tolerance, non-violence etc. Physical activity in an organized way leads to the accomplishing of this social integration process (Ciolcă & Ghițescu, 2019, p.56).

If the children's social development is important to their parents the beginning of the primary school represents a very important moment for kids as they build a social status which is not selective, but it permeates itself unwillingly, because they get the role of child-pupil/child-student (Bartošová et al., 2012, p.18).

The students of the cycle with the basic acquisitions, not only those who are beginners but also those who are used to the phase of scholar initiation are emotionally implied in the activities they have in their schedule and also presents a high interest on the studying the contents of these activities. The interest for the physical activity can be seen in their active behaviour and from this respect the teaching – learning activity within the

physical education class must be stimulated in order to gear the internal and external receivers responsible for the prosocial behaviour (Pană, 2019, p.49).

The physical education in schools led by a real teacher and done regularly, plays an important role in the social integration of the students, especially in this technological period when they spend more time in front of the computers, gadgets (Gulap, 2014, p.106). As a matter of fact, focus is not laid on the social integration but on the technological integration. There must be a balance between all the necessary components of forming a behaviour, not only from a social point of view but also from an academic, motive power, religious and technological point of view.

Following a Spanish survey with 24 pupils of 9-10 years old, the motion games within the physical education class improve the social skills (Madrona et al., 2014, p.8). Within the motion game, interpersonal relationships turn up, and appears some communication which settles the transition to the game itself, maintaining an emotional atmosphere which is common to all the participants (Rukavishnikova, 2016, p.122).

The authors Petrovici and Dobrescu (2013, p.1409) claim that emotional intelligence is based on the ability of controlling emotions, feelings, to adjust them to the specific context, to understand and accept the other children's feelings in order to communicate positively. As at this young age, children live feelings in the social environment without being aware, it is advisable that the development of the emotional intelligence be accomplished from the beginning of the school, concentrate on the stimulation of empathy and the feeling of self-acceptance (Cojocariu & Nechita, 2011, p.265). Physical education has the ability of teaching children the transition of the interaction of the own person to the interrelationship with the others.

2. Purpose Of Study

This work presents the particularities of applying two tests to assess the psychosocial profile and of the ability of objective estimate for the second level pupils, with the aim of building a prosocial behaviour within a specific skill of socializing the pupils of the basic acquisitions cycle. These two ways of assessment try to point out how a strategy focussed on the game method, on the educational ways with active character, on the ways of organizing specific dynamic games, contributes to the improvement of the social attitudes formed to this, deciding the formation of a specific skill.

3. Metodology

The experiment was achieved through the means of a didactic strategy for moulding of specific competence „*Forming a socio-emotional behaviour based on the feeling of friendship, cooperation and participation in the psychomotive power activity*” to three classes in the second form, within three different schools in Arges county: Gymnasium School, No.6/Nicolae Balcescu Pitesti; Gymnasium School, No.16/Ion Luca Caragiale Pitesti; Gymnasium School No.1 Costesti.

There was an instructive – educative design based on games which was applied to these classes; they were done during the second semester of the school year 2018-2019 with the aim of improvement the prosocial behaviour. The games combine the formation and development of the psycho-motive power of the pupils with the stimulation of the psycho-social capacity of these.

In the assessment of the evolution of the pupils’ social attitudes level, I used two tests of assessment. For an easier way of working I used the two tests in capital letters for reading easily and some iconography pictures for illustrating the meaning of some words:

- the first test entitled „***The pshychosocial behavior***” – developed by Zlate Mielu and Zlate Camelia’s model (1982, pp.72-73);

- the second test entitled „***Notice the Colleague***” – the specific method of Zapan Gheorghe (1984, pp.308-314).

The first test „***The Pshychosocial behavior***” (table no.1) deals with the assessment of the social qualities personality features ,with which we managed to determine the psychosocial profile of the pupils’ behaviour. This type of test was intended to be understood by the pupils, being written in capital letters: „*How much , so and so, little ,very little each pupil behaves during the physical education class?*” through which it is suggested the appreciation of the personality features by the colleagues during the physical education class.

Table 1. The test "The psychosocial behavior" - assessment of personality traits

SUB- JECTS/ CLASS STU- DENTS	PERSONALITY FEATURES					
	COOPERATIVE (LISTEN TO THE IDEAS OF OTHERS)	BOSSY (MAKES THE BOSS)	COOPERANT (TALKS TO EVERYONE)	POPULAR (EVERYONE LIKES IT)	AGRESIV (LOOKING WITH EVERYONE)	CREATIV (KNOWS HOW TO INVENT)
A.A.						

Source: table arising from the original research activity

With the help of Likert's dial (table no.2) changed in order to be understood by the pupils to offer right answers, each pupil expressed the appreciation level for every six personality features, for each colleague in the class.

Table 2. Adapting the Likert scale

Likert scale				
Nr. Crt.	Academic presentation	Presentation of children	Abbreviation in the table	Scores
1	To a very large extent	very much	which corresponds to the letter A	5
2	Largely	A lot	which corresponds to the letter B	4
3	To some extent	so and so	which corresponds to the letter C	3
4	To a sall extent	little bit	which corresponds to the letter D	2
5	To a very small extent	Very little	which corresponds to the letter E	1

Source: table arising from the original research activity

The second test „*Notice the colleague*” deals with the ability of appreciation and self-appreciation through the means of assessing the self-knowledge and also the level of their colleagues’ knowledge, being a compulsory feature for the integration in the society. The test implies a practical check-up – the crossing of an applied route being performed right and efficiently and not in some short time, and a written verification – a questionnaire in which the pupils are asked to name the first four competitors who have performed the route correctly and the first four who haven't. A special aspect is that among the eight competitors, the pupils can nominate themselves, either good or bad.

The research has aimed the elaboration and experimentation of a didactic approach adjusted for the pupils' age, focused on the game method, in which 43 dynamic games have been projected, used in the second semester of the second form. The experiment has begun with an initial test, at the end of the first semester, before the implying the instructive – educative design in order to establish the level of the psychosocial attitudes, as well as a final one at the end of the second semester, before the end of school year 2018-2019, to notice the evolution of social features at the end of the experiment, determined by the dynamic games during the physical education classes.

We should mention that the number of pupils in the three classes is different from the initial test to the final one. The reason of this is the scholar transfer during the period between the semester, within the intersemestrial holiday.

Table 3. Number of subjects participating in the initial and final tests

Educational establishment	Initial test			Final test		
	G	B	Total	G	B	Total
Secondary School No.6 / Nicolae Bălcescu Pitești	17	13	30	16	13	29
Secondary School No. 16 / Ion Luca Caragiale Pitesti	12	13	25	12	14	26
Costești Secondary School No. 1	5	21	26	5	21	26

Source: original data resulting from research

In table no.3 there are differences recording the number of pupils in the two tests initial and final at two classes out of three. In this respect, at School no.6, we have a schoolgirl performing only in the first semester and then being transferred to another school in the second semester. At school no.16 it is an opposite situation a schoolboy who hasn't been present at the initial tests as he has been transferred in the second semester at that respective school. Therefore, we have a pupil who has performed the initial tests and in a different class there is a pupil who has performed only the final tests, the evolution of the two unable to be analysed.

4. Results and discussions

4.1. The comparable analyse and interpreting the initial and final test results at the “Psychosocial behaviour”test

The results of the two tests have been verified statistical mathematically, being calculated the arithmetic means for all the six personality features and the diagram for each pupil's psychosocial profile is

designed in pictures 1-3, in blue-the initial test and in red-the final test. The interpretation of the psychosocial profile has the following results:

- the features above 3 are considered positive ones;
- the features that are equal to 3, are not available, as it means the members opinions are different;
- the features below 3 are considered negative ones.

There are two negative personality features, out of six, which every pupils should appreciate about their colleague's behaviour, and the appreciation level should be under 3 in order to be positively interpreted regardless to their table position. By comparing the results at the two tests, there can be seen the evolution of the pupils' psychosocial behaviour for all 3 classes, being somelight progress at the final test. However, some of the pupils' behaviour features are lied below 3. This experiment dealt with the second form pupils of the compulsory scholar system where there is no general competence, therefore no specific competences for building interpersonal relationships of the prosocial active behaviour. That is why, in spite of the swall average of progress concerning the development of social abilities, the formation and improvement process scored a positive evolution, on the basis of a didactic strategy focussed on some specific competence „*The outline of a social-emotional behaviour based on friendship, colaboration and cooperation in the psycho-motive power activity*”, emphasizing an evolution of all personality features used in this class of curriculum cycle of basic knowledge.

The results analysis reveals that the research includes pupils of 8-9 years old, who need more time to express their social potential and forming of a specific competence in this plan. Therefore, the elaboration of a general competence and specific socializing competences within the basic knowledge cycle at the physical education as a school subject, performing it through the means of some strategies adjusted for the pupils'age focussed on games, makes easier the social communication abilities, cooperation, colaboration, offering the necessary background for their development in the first classes of school, third and fourth forms to improve their social abilities initiated at the end of second form.

We consider that physical education forms „the abecedarium of the social abilities” which are vital for building a strong personality since the early basic acquisitions.

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Figure 1. Dynamics of the psychosocial profile of the students of the second grade of School No. 6 Pitești
Source: authors' own contribution

Figure 2. Dynamics of the psychosocial profile of students of the second grade of School No. 16 Pitesti
Source: authors' own contribution

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Figure 3. Dynamics of the psychosocial profile of students of the second grade of School No. 1 Costesti
Source: authors' own contribution

By checking-up the profiles of all the pupils we can notice that at the final test, the evolution of the interpersonal behaviour to the right, even if to some pupils number 3 is not surpassed, it is demonstrated that by using the dynamic games in the formation and development of social attitudes we managed to perform positively in the way of the six personality features.

In the second form of School No.6/Nicoale Balcescu, the pupil D.A presents huge differences in many ways ,succeeding in being more cooperative (from 3,72 to 4,14), more talkative (from 3,65 to 4,07) and less aggressive (from 2,10 to 1,6) and the pupil R.M is shown as one who succeeds in tempering his authority (from 2,48 to 1,64) his aggressivity (from 2,10 to 1,60) and manages to develop his creative ability (from 2,62 to 3,03).

In the second form at School No.16 /Ion Luca Caragiale, the average of the pupils who shows progress is much more than that of School No.6/Nicoale Balcescu. Among them, we can present you pupil C.A., who manages to temper his authority (from 4 to 3,44) and aggressivity (from 3,33 to 3), with the best results in communication (from 3,83 to 4,12). The pupil G.A. becomes more talkative (from 3,92 to 4,28) and more creative (from 3,91 to 4,48) while his popularity has risen among his colleagues from (2,54 to 2,48). The pupil P.A. has gained progress on many plans, becoming less bossy (from 2,54 to 1,84) and less aggressive (from 2 to 1,4) while at cooperation (from 3,33 to 3,92), his popularity (from 1,91 to 2,84) and his creativity (from 3 to 3,72) having huge limits of the progress.

The comparison with the two classes of the two different schools, the pupils in School No. 1 Costesti have registered the most positive changes. We can present those pupils who have had some big progress concerning the interpersonal behaviour ,some of which involving in all the plans:

- the pupil D.C manages to have a more cooperative behaviour (from 2,04 to 2,56) and much less bossy (from 3,56 to 2,88);
- the pupil D.D manages to evolve in cooperation even if he registered a positive result in the initial test succeeding in having the maximum at the final test (from 4,44 to 4,8) while in popularity he has reached a positive status (from 2,88 to 3,2);
- just like D.D the pupil I.M. evolves in cooperation reaching the peak (from 4,56 to 4,92) his authority getting down (from 1,6 to 1,2) while popularity being a little bit higher (from 3,36 to 3,76);
- the pupil V.E. manages to reach evolutive limits for five features , cooperation (from 3,32 to 4,32), authority (from 3,52 to 2,8),

- communication (from 3,52 to 4,2) agresivity (from 3,16 to 2,12) and creativity (from 2,48 to 3,42);
- the pupil C.E. has a great cooperation level (from 2,48 to 3,04) , develops some communication (from 3,2 to 3,84) and creativity (from 2,32 to 3,08) much better;
- the pupil G.A. shows a more cooperative attitude (from 3,2 to 3,72),a greater communicative ability (from 3,32 to 4) his popularity (from 1,72 to 2,32) and some important creativity (from 3,04 to 3,72);
- the pupil S.A. registers the most important progress in cooperation (from 2,6 to 4,2) and in communication (from 2,8 to 4,24) while the creativity is not as high as the others (from 2,36 to 3,36);
- we also have two pupils who present progress in all the six personality features, J.M. and N.A.

Table 3. Initial and final test results of J.M. and N.A. - School No. 1 Costesti

	J.M.		N.A.	
	T.I	T.F	T.I	T.F.
Cooperating	2.32	3.16	2.76	4.04
Bossy	3.8	2.84	2.52	1.8
Communicative	2.64	3.12	3.4	4.12
Popular	1.68	2.12	1.52	2.12
Aggressive	3.96	2.92	2.2	1.56
Creative	2.84	3.44	2.56	3.32

T.I – initial test

T.F – final test

Source: authors'own contribution

Each pupil's evolution is different ,is complex, they sometimes evolves and some other times they stop, they have different levels of development or some of them evolve in all the plans of research.

Judging by all the graphs, we can now say that performing the physical education class by using dynamic games as instructive – educative means for the basic acquisitions cycle, determines the formation and development of psychosocial attitudes which are vital for a prosocial behaviour in a society.

4.2. Comparative analysis and explanation of the initial and final results at the test „Notice the colleague”

The processing procedure of the data in the sociometric questionnaire consisted of the arranging the pupils' answers into the sociometric dial, being calculated the some of the positive answer for each pupil. There was designed a scoring regarding the right order of the pupils depending on the value of their positive and negative appreciations.

At the same time, the teacher draws a scoring of all the pupils, then he report all the information by comparing the results made by the pupils with those of the teacher. The appreciations implied strictly the performing and the ability of obeying the rules and following all the instructions of the teacher at the beginning of the route.

In table No. 4 there are drawn the scorings of the three classes in the initial and final tests. By comparing the results, one can see how the instructive-educative means contributed to the formation and educating the capacity of appreciating the pupils' evolution but also the ability of self-appreciation. The content of the games laid focus on the awareness of the behaviour image of the colleagues and the image itself.

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Table 4. The ranking of the objective assessments of the students correlated with the ranking of the objective assessments of the teacher at the three second grades

School No.6 / Nicolae Bălcescu Pitești				School No.16/Ion Luca Caragiale				Secondary School No.1 Costești			
Initial test		Final test		Initial test		Final test		Initial test		Final test	
Teacher classification	Classification students	Teacher classification	Classification students	Teacher classification	Classification students	Teacher classification	Classification students	Teacher classification	Classification students	Teacher classification	Classification students
1	D.Y.	1	D.Y.	1	C.A.	1	I.M.	1	N.A.	1	D.A.
2	G.A.	2	A.L.	2	B.E.	2	C.A.	2	D.A.	2	R.E.
3	L.M.	3	B.A.	3	G.A.	3	I.C.	3	A.M.	3	P.C.
4	M.S.	4	G.A.	4	I.M.	4	B.N.	4	D.B.	4	B.R.
5	D.R.	5	F.V.	5	P.E.	5	U.B.	5	D.L.	5	S.R.
6	A.L.	6	S.C.	6	F.V.	6	D.R.	6	D.R.	6	D.M.
7	S.G.	7,5	D.A.	7	S.C.	7	S.C.	7	G.A.	8	D.B.
8	R.M.	7,5	D.Ș.	8	L.M.	8	D.Ș.	8	T.M.	8	D.L.
9	S.C.	9	V.N.	9	V.N.	9	S.A.	9	B.R.	8	D.L.
10	O.M.	10,5	D.R.	10	T.L.	10	T.L.	10	S.R.	10	I.L.
11	F.I.	10,5	S.A.	11	F.I.	11,5	C.D.	11	R.R.	11	R.G.
12	P.Ad.	12	N.A.	12	D.R.	11,5	M.S.	12	D.A.	11,5	B.I.
13	D.Ș.	13,5	S.G.	13	S.G.	13	S.G.	13	I.M.	11,5	G.V.
14	S.Ad.	13,5	P.M.	14	R.M.	15	P.Ad.	14	D.A.	13	V.E.
15	N.M.	15	N.M.	15	C.D.	15	P.M.	15	P.C.	14,5	D.D.
16	S.G.	16,5	T.L.	16	N.M.	16,5	F.I.	16	R.E.	14,5	J.M.
17	P.A.	16,5	M.R.	17	P.Ad.	16,5	V.N.	17	I.R.	16	G.I.
18	F.V.	18	O.M.	18	S.A.	18	P.F.	18	G.V.	17	A.M.
19	V.N.	19	M.S.	19	S.A.I.	19	N.M.	19	I.L.	18,5	T.M.
20	B.A.	20	P.Ș.	20	P.M.	20	S.A.I.	20	V.E.	18,5	C.E.
21	R.Ș.	21	P.F.	21	A.L.	21	R.M.	21	G.I.	20	G.A.
22	P.F.	22	F.I.	22	R.Ș.	22	L.M.	22	C.E.	21	N.A.
23	M.R.	23	P.Ad.	23	P.F.	23	S.Ad.	23	B.I.	22	I.R.
24	P.Ș.	24	S.Ad.	24	N.A.	24	A.L.	24	D.F.	22	I.R.
25	N.A.	25	C.D.	25	M.R.	25	D.A.	25	B.A.	23	D.C.
26	S.A.	26	R.M.	26	D.A.	26	P.Ș.	26	R.C.	23	D.R.
27	T.L.	27	P.A.	27	S.Ad.	27	N.A.	27	C.M.	24,5	D.F.
28	C.D.	28	L.M.	28	P.Ș.	28	P.Ș.	28	P.A.	24,5	V.I.
29	D.A.	29	S.A.I.	29	P.A.	29	R.A.	29	V.I.	25	P.A.
30	P.M.	30	R.Ș.					26	Ș.A.	26	P.A.

Source: authors'own contribution

As you can see, at School No.6, in the initial test, both the teacher and the pupils nominated the pupil D.Y. on the first place and N.M. on the 15th place. After the instructive –educative, design was introduced and after the final test, the pupils ability of appreciation/self-appreciation has risen, so that we can have seen pupils at the same level from the point of view of teacher and of the pupils: D.Y. – the 1st place, D.A – the 2nd place, S.C – the 7th place, T.L. – the 10th place, S.G. – the 13th place, P.S. – the 28th place and P.A. – the 29th place .

At School No.16 in the initial test both the teacher and the pupils decided as the first place on pupil only, C.A. In the final test, the pupils appreciated more accurately having six pupils in the pupils scoring and the teacher's too: C.A. – the 2nd place, M.G. – the 6th place, S.A. –the 7th place, I.C. – the 9th place, U.B. – the 15th place, V.V. – the 17th place. The pupil M.G. has the same scoring as S.A. does, the differences between them being done by adding the preference number (that appears in the sociometric dial with + and the denial number -).

Concerning the initial test, at School NO.1 Costesti the pupils' appreciations were different from those of their teacher, while the final test, only 9 pupils have the some scoring: D.A. – the 1st place, S.R. – the 4th place, G.V. – the 13th place, D.C. – the 16th place, P.A. – the 17th place, P.M. – the 18th place, S.A. – the 23rd place, N.A. – the 24th place, I.R. – the 26th place.

The growth of the pupils' identical positions in the final test emphasizes an evolution of the pupils comparing with the initial test which confirms that using the dynamic games in the basic acquisitions cycle, facilitates the formation and manifesting of a specific competence through the means of some prosocial behaviours.

5. Conclusion

The activity within the research demonstrations that the motive-power activities during the physical education class lay stress on the interpersonal abilities and socializing competences.

The results of the research confirm the we can assess objectively the influence of motive power activities within the physical education class in forming and developing the interpersonal relationships abilities and socializing competences, in the second form, the last class in the curricular cycle of basic acquisitions, when the didactic strategy is focused on the play role and the contents are exclusively done by the means of dynamic games.

The pupils' progress of the personality features at the end of the experiment as well as the growth of the objective appreciation/self-

appreciation ability of the pupils confirm that having the two tests in the second form adjusted to the physical education as a school subject ,proved their usefulness in measuring assessing and appreciating the psycho – sociological aspects at the pupils of research .

The two assessment tests concerning the motive power games of measuring the development of the personality level through the means of the awareness pf self-image and the other colleagues' behaviour proved to be selected right, facilitating the correct understanding of the pupils'behaviour.

The usage of the evaluation system of the psychosocial attitudes on the basis of the feedback (received emotion- transmitted emotion) which was suggested by us for this age, emphasizes both the psychometric component and the psychosocial component and it can determine organizing measures for the reorganization of the schoolar groups.

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